

Effects of Cultural Adaptation Processes on Mental Health in Immigrants

Betül YENİAY¹

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Editors Group:

¹ – St. Clemenst University – Clinical Psychology PhD, keremkeskin3461@gmail.com, Orcid : 0009-0001-8930-3926

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Abstract

Globalization and extensive migration have led to people from many cultural origins encountering several challenges in assimilating into new communities. These challenges might adversely impact persons' mental health. This research aims to investigate the impact of stressors, identity conflicts, and social exclusion experienced by immigrants throughout their cultural adaption on their mental health. The research assesses the varying impacts of assimilation, integration, separation, and marginalization techniques on immigrants' mental health. This study specifically investigates the impact of language acquisition, social integration, and social support on mental health. The analysis examines the correlation between events such as discrimination, ethnic identity conflicts, and social exclusion with depression, anxiety, and stress. The results indicate that effective cultural adaptation positively influences the mental health of immigrants. Enhancing social support networks and fostering immigrants' involvement in the integration process, while maintaining their cultural identities, are identified as factors that bolster their psychological resilience. Conversely, prejudice and exclusion have been recognized as primary causes adversely impacting mental health. This research highlights the significance of managing cultural adaption processes and formulating anti-discrimination social policies to enhance the mental health of immigrants.

Keywords : Immigrants, Cultural Adaptation, Psychological Well-Being, Integration Strategies, Social Exclusion, Mental Health, Discrimination.

Introduction

Globalization's escalating migratory patterns influence not only the physical relocation of persons but also their psychological and cultural adaptability (Berry, 1997). The challenges faced by immigrants throughout the integration process into a new culture, including stress, language hurdles, social isolation, and prejudice, might adversely impact their mental health (Bhugra & Becker, 2005). This study examines the correlation between immigrants' cultural adaptation strategies and their mental health from an interdisciplinary perspective, analyzing

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the impact of strategies such as integration, assimilation, separation, and marginalization on levels of depression, anxiety, and stress among immigrants (Schwartz, Unger, Zamboanga & Szapocznik, 2010). Moreover, enhancing social support networks and implementing legislation against discrimination may enhance the psychological well-being of immigrants (Cohen & Wills, 1985).

Method

The research, undertaken by me under the guidance of Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin Yıldırım and Prof. Dr. Derya Berrak Yentür on behalf of St. Clements University, was conducted from January 2024 to September 2024 and seeks to investigate the impact of immigrants' cultural adaptation processes on mental health through an interdisciplinary lens. This research used a mixed-methods approach to investigate the impact of acculturation processes on the mental health of immigrants. The association between acculturation tactics and mental health was examined via the collection of both quantitative and qualitative data, providing a comprehensive viewpoint. Quantitative data were gathered using structured questionnaires and psychometric measures, while qualitative data were obtained via semi-structured interviews.

Sample and Participant Selection:

The research was performed on a cohort of 105 immigrants residing in Turkey. The individuals exhibited diversity for demographic factors, including age, gender, educational attainment, and length of migration. This research, done in locations with a substantial immigrant population like as Istanbul, Ankara, and Izmir, sought to examine cultural disparities.

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Data Collection Tools:

Quantitative data were gathered using measuring instruments including the Acculturation Scale, Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS-21), and Social Support Scale. Semi-structured interviews were undertaken to get a comprehensive grasp of the unique experiences and challenges faced by immigrants.

Data Analysis:

Quantitative data were evaluated with SPSS 26.0 software. Correlation analysis, t-tests, and ANOVA were used to assess the associations between cultural adaption techniques and mental health. Qualitative data were analyzed by thematic analysis, resulting in the identification of primary themes from the interview data.

Conceptual Framework and Literature Review

Migration is the permanent or temporary relocation of persons or groups from one designated location to another. Migration is categorized into several sorts, including forced migration, voluntary migration, seasonal migration, and internal movement (Castles & Miller, 2009; Yentür, 2022). Forced migration occurs due to factors such as conflict, natural disasters, or human rights abuses, while voluntary movement is undertaken by those seeking better living circumstances. The notions of migrant and refugee have significant relevance in this setting. Migrants often seek improved living circumstances, while refugees are those escaping persecution or conflict and seeking international protection (UNHCR, 2020; Yentür, 2022).

There are notable distinctions between these two groups; although refugees possess rights under international law, immigrants often relocate for economic or social motivations. The demographic attributes of immigrants fluctuate based on variables such as age, gender, educational attainment, and profession. Typically, younger and better educated persons have a higher propensity to move; yet, elderly folks may also relocate for diverse causes (OECD, 2019;

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Yentür, 2022). The demographic features significantly influence the adaption processes and mental health of immigrants.

Acculturation is the process by which people adjust to a new cultural milieu. This process includes the assimilation and incorporation of cultural values, beliefs, and actions (Berry, 1997; Yentür, 2022). The adaptation process profoundly influences people' psychological and social well-being. Cultural adaptation tactics include assimilation (complete absorption into the new culture), integration (coexistence of two cultures), separation (rejection of the new culture), and marginalization (exclusion from both cultures) (Berry, 2005; Yentür, 2022). Each of these techniques has distinct influences on the mental health of immigrants. Cultural shock refers to the discomfort and disorientation people have while transitioning to a new culture. This process may impair people' capacity to adapt to their new surroundings and result in mental health issues (Ward & Kennedy, 1999; Yentür, 2022). Immigrants may face challenges in the adaption process when confronted with differing norms and values. The cultural adaption process may present several challenges, including linguistic obstacles, social isolation, prejudice, and economic hardships. The challenges might adversely impact the mental health of immigrants and complicate the adaption process (Schmitt et al., 2014; Yentür, 2022). Mental health pertains to the cognitive, emotional, and social well-being of persons (WHO, 2004). Psychological well-being encompasses an individual's capacity to manage life's challenges and overall life happiness. Mental health is intricately linked to social support, stress management, and personal resilience (Keyes, 2002; Yentür, 2022). Psychological well-being include elements such as self-efficacy, social connections, the pursuit of meaning, and emotional control. These components are crucial in the adaption processes of immigrants. Immigrants may encounter risk factors including linguistic challenges, cultural disparities, and social ostracism. Such circumstances may elevate the likelihood of anxiety, depression, and other mental health issues (Bhugra, 2004; Yentür, 2022).

The process of cultural adaptation enables people to acclimate to a new culture, yet challenges in adaptation may elevate stress levels. Cultural adaptation is intrinsically linked to mental health; challenges encountered throughout the adaptation process may result in stress and anxiety (Ozer et al., 2016; Yentür, 2022). Immigrants engage in the redefinition of their identities while attempting to assimilate into a new culture. This process may result in

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psychologically intricate feelings and impact people' mental health (Phinney, 1990; Yentür, 2022). Social support significantly influences the adaption processes of immigrants. Supportive social networks may alleviate stress and enhance mental health (Taylor, 2001; Yentür, 2022). Discrimination and exclusion significantly impair the mental health of immigrants. Such circumstances may result in psychological stress and jeopardize persons' mental health (Williams & Mohammed, 2009; Yentür, 2022).

A multitude of research exist in the literature about the impact of cultural adaptation on mental health. These research investigate the correlation between the adaptation process and people' mental health state, highlighting the impact of several techniques (Miller & Kobayashi, 2019; Yentür, 2022). Literature studies concerning the mental health of immigrants highlight the frequency of psychological issues, including stress, anxiety, and depression, as well as the correlation between these issues and cultural adaption processes. Integration strategies significantly influence the psychological well-being of immigrants (Kok & Ersanilli, 2013; Yentür, 2022). Effectively formulated policies may enhance people' societal standing and favorably influence their mental well-being. Intercultural disparities profoundly influence individual mental health (Hofstede, 2001; Yentür, 2022). The challenges faced by people from diverse cultural origins may result in the development of mental health issues.

Theoretical Framework

Acculturation is pivotal in the assimilation of immigrants into a new society. Berry's Acculturation Model delineates immigrants' endeavors to achieve social acceptability while preserving their ethnic identities via the techniques of assimilation, integration, separation, and marginalization (Berry, 1997). Social identity theory highlights the influence of social groupings on individual identities and its impact on mental health (Tajfel & Turner, 1986). Stress and coping theories investigate the methods by which immigrants manage the challenges they encounter and elucidate the impact of stress on mental health (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Intercultural communication and adaptability underscore the significance of cultural disparities that immigrants face in their encounters with new communities (Gudykunst, 2005). Simultaneously, experiences of prejudice and social isolation are variables that adversely

impact immigrants' mental health (Williams, 2007). Theories of systematic discrimination and social dominance elucidate the foundational role of social structure in these experiences (Bobo & Kluegel, 1993; Sidanius & Pratto, 1999), whereas the psychological ramifications of social exclusion present a significant issue (Williams, 2007). Social support theory highlights the significance of familial and communal assistance in safeguarding the mental health of immigrants (Cohen & Wills, 1985). Immigrants' social support networks enhance their psychological well-being by favorably influencing their acculturation processes (Romero, 2013).

Summary of the Study and Findings

This research was carried out at St. Clements University under the direction of Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin Yıldırım and Prof. Dr. Derya Berrak Yentür. The objective of the research was to investigate the impact of immigrants' acculturation processes on mental health within an interdisciplinary framework. The research involved 105 immigrant participants and aimed to examine the correlation between acculturation strategies (integration, assimilation, separation, and marginalization) and mental health, as well as the influence of social support systems and the impact of experiences such as exclusion and discrimination.

The results indicate that persons exhibiting elevated acculturation levels have reduced scores in depression (30% mild, 40% moderate, 20% severe), anxiety (25% mild, 35% moderate, 25% severe), and stress (35% mild, 30% moderate, 20% severe). Substantial correlations were identified between the Acculturation Scale and the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS-21), hence affirming the criterion validity of the measures. Furthermore, discriminant validity evaluations revealed minimal associations between the Acculturation Scale and other measures assessing distinct notions, suggesting that discriminant validity was attained. The study used a hybrid technique, including both quantitative data obtained via questionnaires and face-to-face interviews. The data gathering procedure started in January 2024 and concluded in June 2024. The gathered data was examined using SPSS 26.0 software, employing correlation, t-tests, and ANOVA tests.

Findings

The study findings distinctly demonstrate the impact of issues such as cultural disparities, social isolation, and prejudice encountered by immigrants on their mental health. The procedures by which immigrants navigate linguistic limitations, social adaptation challenges, and economic hardships significantly impact their psychological well-being.

Social support networks, particularly familial and communal assistance, are essential in enhancing immigrants' capacity to manage stress and sustain their mental well-being. Immigrants using integration tactics have superior psychological well-being when cultural adaptation strategies are analyzed. Conversely, those who use marginalization and separation methods are seen to encounter more mental health issues.

Research indicates that traumas experienced by refugee and asylum seeker populations result in significant psychiatric illnesses, including post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). Socially accepted immigrants have greater psychological resilience, but those subjected to exclusion and prejudice experience detrimental effects on their mental health.

Demographic Findings

Demographic characteristics of 105 immigrants participating in the study were examined in terms of age, gender and educational status.

Age Distribution:

35% (37 people) 25-34 years old

25% (26 people) 35-44 years old

20% (21 people) 18-24 years old

15% (16 people) 45-54 years old

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5% (5 people) 55 years of age and above

Gender Distribution:

Female: 52% (55 people)

Male: 48% (50 people)

Educational Status:

Primary education: 10% (11 people)

Secondary education: 20% (21 people)

High School: 30% (32 people)

University: 30% (32 people)

Master's/Doctorate: 10% (9 people)

The study used the Acculturation Scale to evaluate the adaption processes of immigrants to social norms, language, and values. The mean acculturation score was calculated as 3.2, with

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40% of individuals reporting a moderate degree of adaptation, 35% a high level of adaptation, and 25% a poor level of adaptation.

Data on the duration of immigrants' stay in Turkey show that 30% of the participants have been in Turkey for 1-2 years, 30% for 2-5 years. Long-term settlers (more than 5 years) constitute only 10%.

Psychological Health Findings

In the analyses made using the DASS-21 scale, the mental health status of the immigrants was determined as follows:

Depression: Average 7.4, 40% moderate, 30% mild, 20% severe depression symptoms.

Anxiety: Average 6.8, 35% moderate, 25% mild, 25% severe anxiety symptoms.

Stress: Average 8.2, 35% show mild, 30% moderate, 20% severe stress symptoms.

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Data derived from the Social Support Scale indicate that 45% of participants reported high levels of social support, 35% reported moderate levels, and 20% reported low levels.

Analysis of the correlation between cultural adaptation and mental health revealed that those exhibiting high levels of adaptation had reduced levels of sadness ($r = -0.45$), anxiety ($r = -0.38$), and stress ($r = -0.42$). The results indicate that several variables influence the mental health of immigrants, with acculturation processes, social support networks, and coping techniques for prejudice playing substantial roles in their impact on mental health. The social acceptance of immigrants significantly contributes to enhancing their psychological well-being.

Discussion and Conclusion

Research unequivocally illustrates the impact of acculturation tactics used by immigrants on mental health. The four primary techniques delineated in Berry's (1997) Acculturation Model—integration, assimilation, separation, and marginalization—are intrinsically linked to the mental health of immigrants.

The results corroborate the notion that the integration technique is the most beneficial method for immigrants to acclimate. The depression, anxiety, and stress levels of immigrants using the integration technique were much lower than those utilizing other tactics. This indicates that immigrants maintain an equilibrium that enables both the maintenance of their cultural identities and the adaption to new social norms.

Conversely, those using the marginalization technique have a greater prevalence of mental health issues, including elevated levels of melancholy and stress. The integration technique may compel immigrants to relinquish their cultural identities, resulting in identity loss and issues with belonging. Research indicates that persons favoring integration have elevated levels of melancholy and anxiety.

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Social support serves as a crucial protective element for the mental well-being of immigrants. Research indicates that immigrants possessing robust social support networks have reduced levels of melancholy, anxiety, and stress. In this setting, support from family and friends aids people in managing challenges and enhances their psychological resilience. Insufficient social support heightens the likelihood of mental health issues among immigrants. Individuals with little social support exhibit elevated levels of sadness, anxiety, and stress. The study also demonstrates the detrimental impact of prejudice and exclusion on the mental health of immigrants. Research indicates that persons experiencing prejudice have markedly elevated levels of melancholy, anxiety, and stress. Language obstacles and economic challenges faced by immigrants adversely impact their mental health by limiting their engagement in social activities. Language inadequacy amplifies feelings of isolation and marginalization, whilst financial hardships elevate stress levels.

The notions of cultural identification among immigrants significantly impact mental health. Individuals who adjust to changing social standards while preserving their cultural identity have superior mental health relative to those who encounter identity conflict. The results substantiate the beneficial impact of immigrants' identity discussions on mental health. The study's findings provide a novel addition to understanding the correlation between immigrants' cultural adaption tactics and mental health, highlighting that the integration strategy is the most beneficial approach for immigrants. Furthermore, it is essential to enhance social support networks, formulate anti-discrimination regulations, and expand initiatives designed to address linguistic obstacles. This research demonstrates that formulating ways to enhance the psychological well-being of immigrants is a significant social need.

IRRITABILITY

The study's flaws arise from its focus on a particular sample, rendering the results unrepresentative of other immigrant populations. The cross-sectional design also restricts the capacity to monitor long-term consequences.

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